

Influence of Job Stress on Married Female Teachers' Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on influence of job stress on married female teachers' performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Striving to achieve the set goals of this study, four specific objectives, four research questions and four hypothetical statements in the null form were developed and put forward to enable the respondents provide answers to the research questions. Current and related literature was extensively viewed and necessary relationships between the key variables (independent and dependent) were developed and reviewed, the study anchored on Stress Response Theory. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of this study comprised of Eight Hundred and Twenty Seven (827) female teachers of public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Random Sampling Technique was used to select the sample size of 330 respondents from 31 secondary schools in the study area of which is 40% of the population. The instrument used for data collection was self-structured questionnaire. The mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the research questions; while the z-test statistic was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that job stress such as work overload, time pressure, physical condition and working hours affect the efficiency and task accomplishment of married female teachers. The study recommended that female married teachers should be given kin priority in terms of job and they should allow them to concentrate more on their teaching work to boost their performance; government should cut down teachers' workload that they would make teaching job more effective; adequate provision should be made for re-training of practicing teachers on time management in secondary schools to deal with teachers' job stress and their perceive burnout, and government should design a programme that would help teachers to deal with health challenges to enable them overcome job stress and students misbehaviour.

Keywords: Influence, Job Stress, Married Female, Teachers' Performance, Time Pressure, Physical Condition, Working Hours

INTRODUCTION

Job stress is considered to be one of the leading work related health problems in the works of life, especially in developing countries where job stress had become the single greatest source of stress and strain among workers. Married female teacher's stress is a much talked of phenomena, however there is little consensus between different professional groups, that stress is a real phenomenon with a range of causal factors including individual vulnerability and systematic influences (Jackson, 2014). Job stress as

complex phenomena is a very subjective experience: what may be a challenge for one person would be a stress free for another. It depends largely on one's background experience, temperament and environmental condition. Stress is a concept that was credited to Abualoush (2018) defined stress as 'a state manifested by a syndrome which consists of all the nonspecifically induced changes in a biologic system.' This stereotypical response pattern, called the 'General Adaptation Syndrome' (GAS), proceeds in three stages. The alarm reaction comprises an initial shock phase and a subsequent counter shock phase. The shock phase exhibits autonomic excitability, an increased adrenaline discharge, and gastro-intestinal ulcerations. The counter shock phase marks the initial operation of defensive processes and is characterized by increased adrenocortical activity.

Job stress is that which derived specifically from conditions in work place, these may either cause stress initially or aggravate the stress already present due to other sources. People appear to be working longer hours more strenuously to meet expectation of job performance. Competition among workers is sharp, there is always someone else ready to "step into some ones shoes" should one be found wanting.

Employee Performance can be described as responses in the form of behaviors reflecting what has been learned by the employee or the kind of training that the employee has received; it encompasses the outcome of the mental and psychological capabilities. Employee Performance is a concept that is increasingly popular amongst scholars of management sciences, as employee performance is vital to both individual and the organization. Employee Performance contributes to the overall betterment of the processes of the organization particularly in terms of efficiency and productivity (Abualoush, 2018).

Employee performance has linkage to the activities and tasks employees carry out in effective and efficient manner, and it also dictates how much employees contribute to the organization and among the contributions of employees are output quantity, work attendance, and accommodating attitude. Furthermore, the financial or non-financial outcomes of the employee which are closely related to the performance and success of the organization is also reflected by employee performance (Anitha, 2014). In regards to the notion of performance, it is measurable using different mechanisms and in general, performance encompasses what is done or not done by employee. It entails the full outcome or success of a person during specific periods of duty as opposed to the predetermined and established standard of work and targets or criteria. Performance is the product of the capacity of employee, multiplied with support and effort. Hence, reduction or nonexistence of one factor will cause decrease in performance.

Stress may however be seen as having two dimensions. "First, there is experiential aspect, that leads to psychological state of body system distress or tension where an individual may have an unpleasant feeling. Then there is physiological aspect which can be perceived as in threatening situation the body responded with a "fight or flight" syndrome According to Wong & Cheuk, (2015) stress is the general term applied to the pressure people felt in life. As a result of these pressures, employees develop various symptoms of stress that can harm their job performance. Hassan, (2017) considered Stress as an 'arousal reaction (positive or negative) to some job personal related stimulus.' The stimulus that causes stress is called a stressor. Stress is positive if it enable a person to perform or excel in a given situation or event.

Health/physical condition of female teacher is a situation that has gain serious attention in the teaching profession which include, the class size of the students, the school facilities which include the buildings, noise level of the students and inadequate learning resources. These factors have very significance depending on the particular circumstances of the school themselves. Teachers in public secondary schools with smaller students population ratios were more likely to see class size as creating little or no stress and also less likely to use ineffective or undesirable teaching methods. Other examples of stressors include, role conflict, role ambiguity, discipline problems, time pressure, bad working conditions, self-respect, inadequate support from friends, family and colleagues, and low student motivation (Chan 2020). In view of this, the study tends to examine the effect of job stress on the performance of married female teachers in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Conceptual Review

Concept of Job Stress

Job stress happens to employee when there is mismatch between the demands of the job and the existence of capabilities and resources of the employee to meet those demands. While according to Salami (2021), job stress is defined as the experience of unpleasant negative emotions such as tension, depression, anger, frustration, and anxiety which result from different aspects of work. Job stress is also faced by employees in a situation where work related factors interact with employees in a situation that disrupt their physiological conditions forcing them to deviate from normal functioning.

Stress is defined according to Kyriacou (2021), as an environmental problems manifested by a state of disequilibrium in an individual, as he or she responds to demand made on him. Stress may be seen as “a state of psychological and physiological imbalance resulting from the disparity between situational demand and the individuals’ ability and motivation to meet that demand. Derogatis (2014), described stress in terms of an uncomfortable emotional experience or feeling of pressure influenced by a person’s personality, environment and emotional response. It is generally agreed that stress involved discomfort and pressures,

Job stress is a serious work hazard which has the power to bring crisis on teachers. In recent time, many studies have examined job stress in the teaching profession. Studies have suggested that teachers experience disproportionate high level of stress. Hammond (2021) reported that 30% of novice teachers exit the profession prior to their 50 years. The major reasons given for this exit was the level of occupational stress experienced by the researchers. Increase work load, a hostile environment, large classes, delay and non-payment of salaries, poor working environment, poor condition of service, parents insult and assaults and time pressure have been identified as sources of job stress. It is the body’s response to any undesirable, mental, physical, emotional, social or environmental demand. Mullms (2022) conceived stress as a complex and dynamic concept. It is a source of tension and frustration which can arise through a number of interrelated influences on behaviour including the individual, group, organization and environmental factors. Telsang (2021) added that stress is refers to a state of mind which reflects certain bio-chemical reactions in human body and it is exhibited in forms like a sense of anxiety, tension and depression.

In human terms any situation that is seen as burdensome, threatening, ambiguous or boring likely to induce stress. This is type of situation that would normally strike the individual as deserving immediate attention or concern and is viewed as unfortunate or annoying. Teachers are at increased risk for burnout. Measuring teachers stress is important and can play important role understanding the process that lead to teachers’ burnout. Burnout is described as the inability to perform both functionally and effectively in employment setting due to extensive to job related stress (Dorman, 2013).

“Stress” As being seen in school; it is a fact of life. The key issue is to personally and systemically ensure that the inevitable stresses are address, lest the burnout risks escalate if the stresses spiral unabated and unchecked, the notion of teachers being at greater burnout risk than people in other professions. Commet (2022) Says Burnout: the cost of caring, the very fact that you care about other people puts you at greater risk of burning out than if you did not care. Another of those stress related paradoxes we have mentioned throughout of this research work. You enter the profession in the first place with high ideals of service to others; this makes you a burnout risk. You daily face lot of red tape, regulations and mandates in a profession with high expectation by the typically accompanied by relative low salaries, this makes you a burnout risk. You don’t punch a clock, and since you care about what you do, you typically take work home with you, this makes a burnout risks.

Types of Stress

Stress management can be complicated and confusing because there are different types of stress. Miller and Smith (2021), gave types of stress as, acute stress, episodic acute stress and chronic stress. Each with it’s own characteristic, symptoms, duration and treatment rapprochement. Let’s look at each one in detail.

i) **Acute Stress:** Acute stress is the most common form of stress. It comes from demands and pressures of the recent past and anticipated demands and pressures of the near future. Acute stress disorder (ASD) is an anxiety disorder characterized by a cluster dissociative and other symptoms occurring within one month of a traumatic event (Dissociation is a psychological reaction to trauma in which the mind tries to cope by “sealing off” some features of the trauma from conscious awareness). By the same token, overdoing on short-term stress can lead to psychological distress, tension, headaches, upset stomach and other symptoms.

Fortunately, acute stress symptoms are recognized by most people. It’s a laundry list of what has gone awry in their lives: the auto accident that crumpled the car fender, the loss of an important contract, a deadline they are rushing to meet, their child’s occupational problems at schools, and so on. Because it is short terms, acute stress does not have enough time to do the extensive damage associated with long-term stress. The most common symptoms are: emotional distress some combination of anger or irritability, anxiety and depression, the three stress emotions, muscular problems including tension headaches, back pain, jaw pain and the muscular tensions that lead to pulled muscles and tendon and ligament problems; stomach, gut and bowel problems such as heart burn, acid stomach, flatulence, diarrhea, constipation, and irritable bowel syndrome: transient over arousal lead to elevation in blood pressure, rapid heartbeat, sweaty palms, heart palpitations, dizziness, migraine headaches, cold hands or feet, shortness of breath and chest pain. Acute stress can crop up in any one’s life and it is highly treatable and manageable (Salami, (2021).

ii. **Episodic Acute Stress:** These are those, however, who suffer acute stress frequently, whose lives are so disordered that they are studies in chaos and crisis. They are always in a rush, but always late if something can go wrong, it does. They take on too much, have too many irons in the fire and cannot organize the slew of self-inflicted demands and pressures clamoring for their attention. They seem perpetually in the clutches of acute stress. It is common for people with acute stress reactions to be over aroused, short tempered, irritable, anxious and tense. Often, they describe themselves as having “a lot of nervous energy” always in a hurry, they tend to be abrupt, and sometimes their irritability comes across as hostility. Interpersonal relationship deteriorates rapidly when others respond with real hostility. The work place becomes a very stress places for them.

The cardiac prone people, described by cardiologist, Hassan (2017), are similar to an extreme case of episodic acute stress. This type of people have an “excessive competitive drive, aggressive, impatience, and a harrying sense of time urgency”. In addition there is a “free floating, but well rationalized form of hostility, and almost always a deep seated insecurity. Such people’s characteristics would seem to create frequent episodes of acute stress for these people Hassan (2017) found them to be much more likely to develop coronary heart disease than those people who show an opposite pattern of behaviour.

Another form of episodic acute stress comes from ceaseless worry. “Worry warts” see disasters around every corner and pessimistically forecast catastrophe in every situation. The world is a dangerous, unrewarding, punitive place where something awful is always about to happen. These awful situations also tend to be over aroused and tense, but are more anxious and depressed than angry and hostile. The symptoms of episodic acute stress are the symptoms of extended over arousal; persistent tension, headaches, migraines, hypertension, chest pain and heart diseases. Treating episodic acute stress requires intervention on a number of levels, generally requiring professional helps which may take many months. Often, life style and personality issues are so ingrained and habitual with these individuals that they see nothing wrong with the way they conduct their lives.

iii. **Chronic Stress:** while acute stress can be thrilling and exciting, chronic stress is not. This is the grinding stress that wears people away day after day, year after year. Chronic stress destroys bodies, mind and lives. It wreaks havoc through long-term attrition. It’s the stress of poverty, of dysfunctional families of being trapped in an unhappy marriage or in a despised job or career. It’s the stress that the never ending “troubles” have brought to the people of Northern Ireland, the tension of the middle east have brought to the Arab and Jew, and the endless ethnic rivalries that have been brought to the people of Eastern Europe and the former Soviet Union. Chronic stress comes when a person never sees a way out of a miserable

situation. It's the stress of unrelenting demands and pressures seemingly interminable of time. With no hope, the individual gives up searching for solutions. Some chronic stresses stem from traumatic, early childhood experience that becomes internalized and remain forever painful and present. Some experiences profoundly affect personality (Anitha, 2014). A view of the world or a belief system is created that causes unending stress for the individuals (e.g. the world is a threatening place, people will find out you are a pretender, you must be perfect at all times) when personality or deep seated conviction and beliefs must be reformulated, recovery requires active self-examination, often with professional help.

Causes of Stress to female married Teachers

Teacher today are expected to fulfill so many roles, not the least of which is to actually teach in many places throughout the country they are to perform their "duties: with very little pay. Many teachers find other roles being thrust upon them. Their duties increase while they still have to deal with grading assignments, writing test, and of course teaching class (Melissa 2013) she stated that, the following are some of the causes of stress to teacher; Too much work:- Not only teachers figure out final grades, but they are also cleaning their rooms, gathering lesson plans and performing numerous other required tasks.

Time pressures and deadlines: - Just remembering the deadlines for everything from failure notices to final grades everything can be a real chore.

Apparent lack of support: - Sometimes the administrative staff is less than supportive of the myriad problems faced by the classroom teacher at the end of the year, they too have item they have to complete before the year ends and teacher concerns sometimes take a back seat. Unclear expectations: - This can occur with new teachers or teachers at a new school who are not sure what the end of the year procedure are:

Responsibility for student's grades: - Even though as teachers we know that, students earn their grades, it often feels that parents and students place facing grades on the shoulders of the teachers. This is especially compounded in senior year where the grade means the difference between diploma and no diploma.

Disruptions:- You have just sat down at the end of the day to work on those research papers and realize that a meeting has been called unfortunately. Many responsibilities exist outside the classroom that requires attention. Owais (2020) opined that, the cause of stress to teachers, for outside teaching seems all together a different job with summer vocations, winter vocations and spring breaks. But considering everything that a teacher has to go through every day as these days off do not so much to get a teacher back in the right frame of mind.

Long working hours: Long workload, Rising class sizes, Pressures due to inspection, Changes in curriculum and courses, Changes to assessment and testing requirements, Poor management, Work place bullying, Crumbling school, Pupils misbehavior, Risk of violence from pupils, parents and intruders, Lack of support with bureaucracy form filling and routine tasks. Lack of job security due to redundancy and fixed term contracts, Lack of control over the job, Burden of providing cover, Threat to early retirement arrangement, Denigration of profession by politician and media, Lack of public esteem, Investigation of source of stress among teachers in Britain, reveal that topping on the lists are pupils' poor attitudes, how motivation and general uncooperative. Kyriacou (2021) however opined that, it is the day-to-day occurrence of these problems that account more for their stressful nature. Travers and Cooper suggest that the requirement for married female teachers to work long hours is another source of stress for them.

Physical conditions

These situations that have received attention in the past include class size, unsuitable buildings, noise level and inadequate resources. In this regard, Travers and Cooper (2016) pointed out that these factors do vary in significance depending on the particular circumstances of the schools themselves. One example of poor physical conditions may occur when schools cannot afford to provide up-to-date technologies at the capacity that it may be required for the prescribed syllabus. Furthermore, schools are often designed for different populations or sizes than the actual amount of people accommodated. Factors such as an

amalgamation of schools can lead to poor physical conditions such as overheating and overcrowding in shared rooms, limited storage space, lack of base classrooms, inadequate staff facilities and problems with travel to and from work. In a study of stress and depressive symptoms in newly appointed married female teachers, it was found that teachers who worked in the most adverse school environments showed the most depressive symptoms. Travers and Cooper (2016) investigated the relationship between teachers' perceptions of class size and pupil-teacher ratio as stressful.

Workload

The issue of workload can be divided into two categories, namely role overload and role under-load. Role overload occurs when the expectations and demands of a job exceed the perceived ability of the individual fulfilling the role in question. Newell (2015) and Rice (2018) have referred to two types of role overload, namely qualitative and quantitative role or work overload. Qualitative role overload occurs when individuals perceive that they do not have the abilities and skills to perform the required job. Quantitative role overload, on the other hand, occurs when the individual is expected to do more work in the time allotted for the job than is possible. Billings and Moos (2021) stated that married female teachers experience role overload. This shared stressor may contribute to a sense of job dissatisfaction.

Role under-load occurs when the expectations and demands of the job underutilize the abilities and skills of the individual in question. Qualitative role under-load also occurs when the tasks in question are not mentally stimulating and challenging. Quantitative role under-load results when the individual has too little to do in a job and ends up being bored. The first characteristic is role overload. Michel, (2020) refers to role overload as innumerable task given to an employee which must be completed within the time frame. In a normal sense, role overload happens when work roles requires employee to put more effort and time than he/she has, thus the roles cannot be performed adequately and comfortably In the meantime, role overload can be defined as having too much work tasks but minimum time to do those tasks. One antecedent that is commonly used as a variable in relation to WFC is role overload because it refers to having too many work tasks need to be completed within a particular time period among academic staff in public and private universities in Tukey have shown that role overload can significantly predict time-based and strain-based conflict.

As there is role overload, it makes teachers to side-line their core job as a teacher which is teaching in classroom. The impact of role overload creates a lot of grievances from teachers. Majority of the teachers who are involved in workshop management experience work role overload such as holding positions as a form teacher, advisor for co-curriculum and certain subjects, as well as coordinator for School-based Assessment (PBS) and Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS/KBAT). Work role overload has been found to be a significant antecedent of WFC (Hsiao & Barak, 2014). As work intensifies in a competitive labor market, organizations expect to have more work hours and high productivity from their employees. Meanwhile, employees may believe that meeting those expectations is a requisite for career advancement or for keeping their jobs. Thus, when they spend too much time at the workplace, they will have limited time to fulfill family demands.

Concept of Performance

The concept of performance is deeply rooted in performance management system (PMS). PM has evolved over time by firm who are now pulling down or doing away with the traditional methods of performance appraisal and employing the 360-degree feedback method (Tracy, 2020). But in general, there is no universally acceptable theory about performance. This is true because the level of effectiveness employed in developing and stimulating employees to perform goes a long way to determine how the firm as a whole performs. Every employee makes contributions to the overall performance of the firm as a unit. So, at the point where the performance of an employee fall below what is expected of them; a longer period of time, this would lead to redundancy and as such would need a re-organization of events. This is because for an organization to be successful, employees would first to be successful in their ask or job performance for success to be attained, the living managers must first consider employees with the right,

appropriate, or required skills and qualifications for the job, and develop them accordingly to enable them closely align to stated or predetermined objective of the firm.

In a bid to achieve high performance, such hiring managers conduct performance appraisals performance appraisal regularly to help employee stay on track and periodically check if my improvement has been made especially from the previous performance levels. Performance appraisal is a performance review that is planned to evaluate the work if an employee is against specific standards or criteria put in place as benchmark for every employee of that organization. The idea here is to take a deep look into the activities and outputs of the employee over the past year(s) with the aim of setting new goals, plans and objectives for the coming years. The appraisal of an employee is traditionally a face-to-face meeting between a manager and an employee (Jackson, 2014).

This forms the bases for proper appraisal which is geared toward achieving objectively in the process, and the identification of grey areas that may not have been noticed for consideration. Other performance review types include; ranking, forced distribution, competency review types include; ranking, formed distribution competency-based, MBO, graphic rating scales, and behavioral anchored rating scale. Another aspect of performance that is pivotal in the attainment of task or job performance on the part of the employee is training and development. At the point of entry into the organization, it is expected that sound orientation and induction (indoctrination) should come after proper training and development Programmes have been introduced. It is imperative to note that the training activities is designed to help employees build new skills and enhance existing ones for the performance level currently, while development activities are put in place to focus more on preparing such employee for duties and responsibilities in the future (Cooper, 2016). To attain good performance, employees are expected to collaborate with their supervisors and stay connected with them thereby imbibing skills that would make them adjust accordingly as described by the performance goals.

Since performance is measured by the progress a worker makes an important work-outcomes, employees are expected to narrow their focus to only things that would help them attain stated or predetermine goals. It is only at this point that they will be satisfied with the job they perform. It is true that achieving or attaining one's goal at every point in time causes one to be satisfied with that job, task, or responsibility that are given. This is why it is stated that for one to effectively measure performance, goal attainment and job satisfaction should be paramount.

Employee Performance in an organization is a very important area in the workplace. It can help the organization increase and utilize the capacity of the human resources it has. It translates into good service delivery and interaction in which affects every area of the firm. To achieve this, firms need to make policies that will encourage employee performance. The demand of an organization's service is based in part on the level of service received by the customer. For the service industry which is our focus in this study, the business is based almost entirely on their employee's performance. That is why management must look for different ways of improving employee performance (Owais, 2020).

Employees are highly valued asset in any firm, explains that a successful and productive business can easily be achieved by actively engaging employees in the process of improving the performance. Michael (2020) defines performance in terms of output; "the achievement of the set quantified objectives. Performance is how best an employee is achieving his or her job requirements. High performance rate emanates from the appropriate behavior and effective application of knowledge, skills and expertise. Not all employees are equal in their working; some have high working capabilities regardless of incentives while others may need occasional jumpstart. If well handled with a lot of effectiveness, the result can be even greater hence improving the employees' morale.

Statement of the Problem

Job stress is a very turbulent environment in which some married female teachers conduct their work requires that authorities examine their practices. This is as a result of heavy workload on the female married teachers that has resulted to stress in their profession, workload issues have been a concern of all teachers and teachers' union during the last decade and likely to produce negative outcomes. Past studies have reported that female married teachers felt frustrated. mentally exhausted, excessively worried,

depressed, anxious and at times defensive towards others because of the stress they undergo in their profession, they are saddle with administrative work, marking of students' script, curriculum development and even compelled to teach extra moral classes. Large classes, limited facilities, lack of teachers increases of workload for the female married teachers as a result of this, it has affected their family life in terms of not meeting up with obligations in the family, hence, the study was carry out to examine the effect of job stress on married female teachers performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the influence of job stress on married female teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the extent to which time pressure influences the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis
2. Determine the extent to which physical condition influences the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis
3. Ascertain the extent to which long working hours influences the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. To what extent does time pressure influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
2. To what extent does physical condition influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
3. To what extent do long working hours influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were developed to guide the study.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area on the extent time pressure influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area on the extent physical condition influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area on the extent long working hours influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a survey research method which involves questionnaire. Research design is a blueprint that guides the researcher in his or her study and analysis. The descriptive survey research design is chosen because relevant data will be collected from the teachers by the use of questionnaire. Eight Hundred and Twenty Seven (827) female married teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State consists the population. Port Harcourt Metropolis has 31 secondary schools. The secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State are represented. The sample size of the study is three hundred and thirty (330) female teachers which is 40% of the total population. The researcher therefore used stratified random sampling techniques. The instrument that was used for data collection in the study was a self-structured questionnaire titled: "Influence of Job Stress on Married Female Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (IJSMTJPQ)". The data gathered was analysed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions, while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using z-test. The decision rule was taken based on criterion mean of 2.50, Above the criterion of 2.50 were considered high extent, while below were considered low extent. The null hypotheses where z-calculated

value is greater than the z-critical value of 1.96 was rejected while the null hypotheses where z-calculated value is less than z-critical value of 1.96 was accepted.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What extent does time pressure influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of the extent time pressure influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis

S/No	Item	PHALGA (N ₁ = 160)		OBIOLGA (N ₁ = 170)			
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1.	Most married female teachers make mistakes in respect to accomplishment of task as a result of time pressure	3.20	0.89	HE	3.14	0.89	HE
2.	Lack of task prioritizing affects the accomplishment of task as a result of time pressure	3.12	0.88	HE	3.04	0.87	HE
3.	Poor work schedule affects the task accomplishment of female married teacher	3.17	0.89	HE	3.19	0.89	HE
4.	Married female teachers are most time stress out as a result of trying to accomplish a task	3.01	0.87	HE	2.99	0.86	HE
5.	Time pressure make married female teachers to make mistakes	3.11	0.88	HE	2.87	0.85	HE
Grand Score		3.12	0.88		3.05	0.87	

Source: Field Data 2025.

The data analysis in Table 1 indicated that the respondents agreed on the view that Most married female teachers make mistakes in respect to accomplishment of task as a result of time pressure. The analysis also showed that the respondents accepted the point that lack of task prioritizing affects the accomplishment of task as a result of time pressure. It was also noticed from the study that the respondents agreed that poor work schedule affects the task accomplishment of female married teacher. The analysis also revealed that the respondents accepted the fact that Married female teachers are most time stress out as a result of trying to accomplish a task. The study still indicated that the respondents agreed on the view that Time pressures make married female teachers to make mistakes.

Research Question 2: *What extent does physical condition influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of the extent physical condition influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis

S/ No	Item	PHALGA (N ₁ = 160)			OBIOLGA (N ₁ = 170)		
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
6.	Physical condition affects the accuracy of married female teachers	3.17	0.89	HE	3.14	0.89	HE
7.	Physical condition of the school environment makes married female, teachers to make so many errors during teaching	2.85	0.84	HE	2.76	0.83	HE
8.	Physical condition of school environment affects the performance of married female teachers	3.01	0.87	HE	2.99	0.86	HE
9.	Married female teachers do not accomplish their task properly as a result of the physical condition of school environment	3.11	0.88	HE	2.87	0.85	HE
10.	School physical condition play a vital role on the task accomplishment of female married teachers	2.88	0.85	HE	2.88	0.85	HE
Grand Score		3.00	0.87		2.93	0.85	

Source: Field Data 2025.

The analysis in Table 2 above showed that the respondents accepted the view that physical condition affects the accuracy of married female teachers. The study still revealed that the respondents agreed on the fact that physical condition of the school environment makes married female, teachers to make so many errors during teaching. It was also observed from the analysis that the respondents accepted the point that physical condition of school environment affects the performance of married female teachers. The study indicated that the respondents agreed on the view that married female teachers do not accomplish their task properly as a result of the physical condition of school environment. The analysis still showed that the respondents accepted the point that school physical condition plays a vital role on the task accomplishment of female married teachers.

Research Question 3: *What extent do long working hours influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of the extent work long working hours influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis

S/ No	Item	PHALGA (N ₁ = 160)			OBIOLGA (N ₁ = 170)		
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
11.	Most female married teachers work for a long period of hours as a result of task accomplishment	3.12	0.99	HE	3.16	0.99	HE
12.	Working for a long period of hours affects the performance of married teachers	3.05	0.99	HE	3.10	0.99	HE
13.	Most married teachers does not accomplish high level of task as a result of noise making of students	3.11	0.96	HE	2.87	1.00	HE
14.	Most married teachers does not accomplish their task as a result of poor sitting facilities	3.17	0.91	LE	3.19	0.881	LE
15.	Long period of administrative task affects the academic work of female married teachers	3.11	0.96	HE	2.87	1.00	HE
Grand Score		3.13	0.88		3.04	0.85	

Source: Field Data 2025

The data analysis in Table 3 above revealed that the respondents agreed on the view that Most female married teachers work for a long period of hours as a result of task accomplishment. The analysis still indicted that the respondents accepted the fact that working for a long period of hours affects the performance of married teachers. It was still noticed in the analysis that the respondents agreed on the point most married teachers does not accomplish high level of task as a result of noise making of students. The study showed that the respondents agreed on the fact that most married teachers does not accomplish their task as a result of poor sitting facilities. The analysis also revealed that the respondents accepted the fact view that long period of administrative task affects the academic work of female married teachers.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area on the extent time pressure influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 4: Z-test Analysis of significant difference in the mean ratings of Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area on the extent time pressure influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Status	N	Mean \bar{X}	Standard Deviation	Df	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
PHALGA	160	3.12	0.88	373	1.24	1.96	Accepted
OBIOLGA	170	3.05	0.87				

The analysis on Table 4 indicated that the z-cal of 1.24 is less than the z-crit of 1.96. Therefore, the calculated z-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is less than the given critical value of z-ratio. Therefore, the hypothesis 2 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area on the extent time pressure influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area on the extent physical condition influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 5: Z-test Analysis of significant difference in the mean ratings of Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area on the extent physical condition influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Status	N	Mean \bar{X}	Standard Deviation	Df.	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
PHALGA	160	3.00	0.87	373	1.39	1.96	Accepted
OBIOLGA	170	2.93	0.85				

The analysis on Table 5 showed that the z-cal of 1.39 is less than the z-crit of 1.96. Therefore, the calculated z-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is less than the given critical value of z-ratio. Therefore, the hypothesis 3 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area on the extent physical condition influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area on the extent long working hours influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 6: Z-test Analysis of no significant difference in the mean ratings of Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area on the extent long working hours influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Status	N	Mean \bar{X}	Standard Deviation	Df.	z- cal	z- crit	Decision
PHALGA	160	3.11	0.88	373	0.19	1.96	Accepted
OBIOLGA	170	3.05	0.87				

The analysis on Table 6 revealed that the z-cal of 0.19 is less than the z-crit of 1.96. Therefore, the calculated z-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is less than the given critical value of z-ratio. Therefore, the hypothesis 4 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area on the extent long working hours influence the job performance of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding of the study in research question one reveal that time pressure has a negative influence on task accomplishment to a large extent noting that if the association is negative, then task accomplishment will be low. Thus the time pressure acts as a co-predictor to task accomplishment. This finding is in agreement with the writings of (Melissa 2013). Just remembering the deadlines for everything from failure notices to final grades everything can be a real chore. Sometimes the administrative staff is less than supportive of the myriad problems faced by the classroom teacher at the end of the year, they too have item they have to complete before the year ends and teacher concerns sometimes take a back seat.

The finding of the study on research question two revealed that physical condition and task accomplishment influence married female teachers negativity in Port Harcourt. This is shown that due to the fact that physical condition affects efficiency of married female, physical condition of the school environment makes married female teachers to make so many errors during teaching that physical condition of school environment affects the performance of married female teachers that married female teachers do not accomplish their task properly as a result of the physical condition of school environment this was in line with Travers and Cooper (2016) viewed that poor physical conditions may occur when schools cannot afford to provide up-to- date technologies at the capacity that it may be required for the prescribed syllabus. Furthermore, schools are often designed for different populations or sizes than the actual amount of people accommodated. Factors such as an amalgamation of schools can lead to poor physical conditions such as overheating and overcrowding in shared rooms, limited storage space, lack of base classrooms, inadequate staff facilities and problems with travel to and from work. In a study of stress and depressive symptoms in newly appointed married female teachers, it was found that teachers who worked in the most adverse school environments showed the most depressive symptoms.

The finding of the study on research question three revealed that Most female married teachers work for a long period of hours as a result of task accomplishment, Working for a long period of hours affects the performance of married teachers, most married teachers does not accomplish high level of task as a result of noise making of students, long period of administrative task affects the academic work of female married teachers. Thus, the researcher concluded that long working hours affects task accomplishment of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis. This was in line with Kyiacou (2021) viewed that, it is the day- to- day occurrence of these problems that account more for their stressful nature. Travers and Cooper (2016) the requirement for married female teachers to work long hours is another source of stress for them. Salami (2021) stated that, although many people outside the teaching profession believe that married female teachers have a short working day, the reality is that many married female teachers, particularly those in managerial positions, work far longer hours than expected. Furthermore, many

married female teachers claim to put in excessive working hours at home for marking, preparation, research work and assessing work of students.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that Work overload such as administrative and academic have a significant relationship with efficiency of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Time pressure has a significant relationship with task accomplishment of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Physical condition has a significant relationship with task accomplishment of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Long working hours have a significant relationship with efficiency of married female teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were proffered based on the findings of this study.

1. It is recommended that government should cut down teachers' workload that they would make teaching job more effective.
2. It is recommended that adequate provision should be made for re-training of practicing teachers on time management in secondary schools to deal with teachers' job stress and their perceive burnout.
3. It is recommended that government should design a programme that would help teachers to deal with health challenges to enable them overcome job stress and students misbehaviour.

REFERENCES

- Abualoush, C. . (2018). Assessment of stress and its risk factors among primary school teachers in the Kiang valley, Malaysia. *Global Journal of Health Science*, 2(2), 163-171.
- Anitha, E.A. (2014). Correlates of Job stress among university professors in Nigeria. *The Nigerian journal of counseling* 2 (1 & 2), 117-126.
- Billings, T. & Moos, K. (2021). *Fundamental Skills in Guidance and Counselling*. Cape Coast: Edsam Computers and Publications.
- Commet, L. (2022). Stress, personal characteristics and burnout among first postgraduate year residents: a nationwide study in Taiwan. *Medical Teacher*. 32(5), 400-407.
- Cooper, J. (2016). Gender-related causes of stress in trainee teachers on teaching practice in the school of education, University of Manchester, UK. *Westminster Studies in Education*, 25, 175-186.
- Derogatis, C.L. (2014). An intervention strategy for workplace stress. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*, 41(1), 7-16
- Dorman, H. (2013). The single salary schedule and other issues of teacher pay. *Peabody Journal of Education*, 82, 574-586.
- Hammond, N.J. (2021). Job stressors, personality and burnout in primary school teachers. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 77 (1), 229-243.
- Hassan, N. (2017). Work stress, job satisfaction and organizational commitment among public employees before privatization. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 18,(1).
- Jackson F. (2014). Executive stress: stress is Chief among executives' health problem, Mayo Clinic Jacksonville Newsletters and Health information Retrieved on 19-06-2015.
- Kyriacou, C. (2021). Teacher stress: Directions for suture research. *Educational Review*, 53, 27-35
- Linde, H. (2021). Management of Occupational Stress and Work-Life Balance among women Managers in Indian Industries: A Contemporary issue", *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, 3(2), 75-92.
- Melissa, C. E. (2013). Role Demands, Work-Family Conflict and Motivation: A Proposed Framework. *Global Business & Management Research*, 7(2), 78-87
- Michel, J. S. (2020). Antecedents of work-family conflict: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 30(5), 839-862.
- Miller, J. & Smith, B (2021). As study on stress management of working women in Coimbatore District", *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1, (7), 2231- 5780.

- Mullms, L. (2022). The effects of meditation on teacher perceived occupational stress, state and trait anxiety, and burnout. *School Psychology Quarterly*, 14(1), 13-25.
- Newell, A. (2015). The Dynamics of Psychological Stressors and Management of Human Stress. *Human Resource Journal* (2),104-112.
- Owais, 5. (2020). Causes and effects of mental stress which a teacher goes through in his career and their remedies. Pakistan: National Union of Teachers (NUT) survey.
- Salami, S. O. (2021). Job stress and burnout among lecturers: Personality and social support as moderators. *Asian Social Science*, 7(5), 110-121.
- Telsang, M.T. (2021). “*Faculty perception of stress and coping strategies in Riyadh*” An unpublished *Ph.D Thesis*, Prince Sultan University, Saudi Arabia.
- Wong, K.S. & Cheuk, W. H. (2015). Job- related stress and social support in kindergarten principals: the case of Macau. *International Journal of Education Management*, 19 (3), 183-196